

IMPROVING SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNERS’ COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS THROUGH CONTEXT-BASED LEARNING APPROACH

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Annotation: The current thesis discusses particular challenges which barricade the development of oral proficiency of second language learners and introduces the contextual learning approach as an effective way of improving communicative skill

Key words: contextual learning approach, technology friendly, target language, constructive tool, real-life situation, problem solving skills.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezis xorijiy tilni ikkinchi til sifatida o‘rganayotgan tinglovchilarning gaprish ko‘nikmasini noananviy tarzda kontekst usuli orqali yanada osonroq o‘rganish bo‘yicha qisqacha bayon qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kontekst orqali yondashuvi, texnologiya uchun qulaylik, maqsadli til, konstruktiv vosita, real hayotiy vaziyat, muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyatlari.

Аннотация: В настоящей диссертации обсуждаются потенциал проблемы, которые препятствуют развитию навыков устной речи у изучающих второй язык, и представлен контекстуальный подход к обучению как эффективный способ улучшения коммуникативных навыков.

Ключевые слова: контекстуальный подход к обучению, технологичность, изучаемый язык, конструктивный инструмент, реальная ситуация, навыки решения проблем.

In the modern world it is getting more crucial to able to communicate in foreign languages for the various purposes. However, acquiring a second language is not an easy job for all students. Second language learners face with various challenges when

practicing their foreign languages. One of such troubles occur in their oral productions. The core of the speaking challenges depends on a variety of factors such as misconception of vocabulary and grammatical pattern; lack of self-esteem; fear of making mistakes and the first language affect, etc.

One innovative approach that has gained incredible success in language teaching education is context-based learning. The current method not only develops language proficiency but also allows learners to dig deeper and comprehend the input better in the real-life conditions.

Contextual learning approach helps foreign language students to completely immerse the target language being engaged in the authentic tasks and real-life situations. This method incorporates language acquisition through meaningful contexts. According to Cangara H., et al., 2008, communication is considered to be the bridge as well as a tool to construct the language between teacher and students and students to students. In the meanwhile, the communicative skill reflects the language proficiency level of L2 students. In this case, using a contextual learning method in the second language classes is considered to be one of the effective tools these days. Regarding Anderson L.W. (2001), contextual learning approach enhances foreign language students' higher order thinking skills since they share their ideas through their conversations to comprehend a particular situation by putting their target languages into practice. Vygotskiy L.S. (1978) suggests that teaching a foreign language by means of comprehensible situations increases the productivity. It is remarkably obvious in the productive skills such speaking. One reason for the effectiveness of context-based learning method is that students are highly likely to use background knowledge by which they can easily get the intake due the comprehensible input.

Zemelman S., et al., (1998) states that combining the intake with real life knowledge is a key factor in constructing a target language which allows learners to engage easily in the certain tasks and activities and accomplish them cognitively. The reason for this is that cognitive outcome emerges as long as the task is clear. The task

becomes clear if the context simulates learners’ real-life experiences. As it is observed everything in this process inseparably connected.

Moreover, context-based teaching method is a technology friendly approach which means incorporating cutting-edge technologies help to work in pairs or in a team to do a particular project such preparing a presentation or creating a short story based on the given context integrating their technological experiences with context-based background knowledge. Johnson E.B. (2002) suggest that the integration of the technology and language classes though contextual learning approach makes the second language classes not only meaningful but also fun.

In conclusion, context-based learning offers a dynamic and effective way of the development of the communicative language skills of second language learners. The target language teachers can not only improve the learners’ oral proficiency but also broaden their horizons with the help of contextual learning approach making them put their languages in practice through the meaningful context and authentic tasks and activities.

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